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Trends in the profile of South African postdocs, 2007–2019: local context and global comparisons¹

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Introduction

South Africa has a shorter history of postdoctoral fellows (PDFs) than many other nations. Its public universities only introduced PDF programmes in the early 2000s, but since then PDFs have received increasing attention in South African policy discourse, which may be ascribed to two main reasons. The first is that such fellowships enable doctoral graduates, particularly those from previously disadvantaged groups (i.e. blacks and women), to obtain further experience in research and innovation [National Research Foundation (NRF), 2018], especially as academics in the higher education (HE) sector (Simmonds & Bitzer, 2018).

In addition to this “framing” of such fellowships (Kerr, 2021), PDFs are seen as playing a crucial role in “augmenting” doctoral supervisory capacity at universities [Department of Science and Technology (DST), 2016 & 2019b; Academy of Science of South Africa (ASSAf), 2018]. This capacity is required to alleviate a supervisory “bottleneck” that has been created by the much greater increase, from 1996 to 2014, in the number of PhD-enrolled students (350%) than in the number of PhD-qualified staff (65%). As Breier and Herman (2017) explain, South African universities face a conundrum: they need more academics with PhDs, from previously disadvantaged groups in particular. To do so, they need to produce more PhD graduates. But to do that, they need more staff with PhDs to supervise.

PDFs (as a social pattern) partly solve this conundrum and are therefore functional for the South African HE sector but may also be dysfunctional for some individual PDFs within that sector (Merton, 1968). For example, concerns have been raised by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and others about PDFs as part of the “research precariat [...] who work in positions with little job security, poor compensation and an unclear path to a permanent post” (Woolston, 2020). Qualitative research on PDFs in South Africa also highlights the career-related effects of PDFs being “professionally trapped in limbo” (Simmonds & Bitzer, 2018).

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In its recent STI policy paper on reducing such precarity of academic research careers, the OECD (2021) identifies the need for more evidence on PDFs, noting that countries often do not have a good understanding of even the number of such researchers. The South African annual, national surveys of research and development (R&D) (from here on referred to as the R&D surveys) have been collecting at least some data, mostly from 2007 onwards, on PDFs in the country's HE sector. To date, these figures have only been reported in separate tables, and are yet to be further analysed and interpreted. In doing so, I provide, for the first time, a national, longitudinal description of PDFs in the HE sector over the period 2007–2019. I also compare, where the data exist, South African PDFs with those elsewhere over the same period, as the first step towards addressing the lack of descriptive evidence required as a basis for designing policy uniquely geared towards the management of South African PDFs.

Methodology

Data were sourced from the statistical reports covering the fiscal years 2007/2008 to 2019/2020, as produced by the Centre for Science, Technology and Innovation Indicators (CeSTII) at South Africa's Human Sciences Research Council (HSRC) on the basis of the R&D surveys they undertake annually. In the later reports, figures are also available for the preceding four earlier years, which required consulting and citing only the 2011/2012, 2016/2017 and 2019/2020 reports (HSRC–CeSTII, 2014, 2019 & 2021) for figures pertaining to the period 2007–2019.

The R&D surveys collect data in accordance with the guidelines recommended by the OECD in the Frascati Manual (OECD, 2015, as cited in HSRC–CeSTII, 2021). All public HE institutions are surveyed, using a census approach, although in the past few years 5–7 of the 24 public universities did not respond. The reference period is the year prior to the survey (the first year of the two years in a report's title), and the reports provide the following for PDFs: headcounts (HCs), disaggregated by nationality (South African versus non-South African), and full-time equivalents (FTEs; as a percentage of the HCs, it is used as an indicator of time spent on research).

As regards comparative global figures for the past two decades, the largest surveys of PDFs in terms of number of and countries covered have been (perhaps surprisingly) undertaken by science journals or magazines. The journal *Science* conducted six bi-annual surveys from 2004 to 2012, collecting data from current and former PDFs who were mostly from the USA, Europe, and Asia (Bonetta, 2010). From 2002 to 2013, the magazine *The Scientist* conducted its annual "Best Places to Work for Postdocs" survey among PDFs located mostly in Western Europe, Canada, and the USA (Richards, 2012). The results of these surveys were not published in peer-reviewed outputs and did not include figures relevant to the focus of this paper.

The third and most recent of these multi-national surveys – and one for which the anonymised data I could download (Nature & Shift Learning, 2020) – was conducted in 2020 by the journal *Nature*. A total of 7 670 respondents, representing 93 nations, provided data (Woolston, 2020). Only 54 of the respondents lived in South Africa at the time of the survey, which I deleted from the data set, together with the 381 respondents who were not employed (full- or part-time) in the HE sector, to increase comparability with the R&D survey figures. I analysed the remaining data (n=7 235) to provide a benchmark with which to compare the South African figures. Other benchmarks took the form of figures reported for individual countries, as sourced from the literature.

Results

Number of postdoctoral fellows

In the South African HE sector, approximately 300 PDFs were recorded in 2001 (Holley et al., 2018), and 357 in 2003 (HSRC–CeSTII, 2005). Since then, the numbers of PDFs in that sector have increased quite dramatically, to 2 867 in 2019, although as Figure 1 below shows, the growth has decelerated since 2017.

Figure 1: Number of postdoctoral fellows at South African higher education institutions, 2007–2019.

The steepest growth rate (close to 200%) is observed for the first half of the period (2007–2013). However, from 2010 to 2019, the rate of 143% (from 1 180 to 2 867) is very similar to the 144% increase recorded for Finland (OECD, 2021) and the 142% (from 10 559 to 25 514) for China (Wang & Yang, 2020) over the same period.

Nationality of postdoctoral fellows

From 2011 to 2016, an average of 62% of the PDFs in South Africa's HE sector were not South African citizens. The percentage increased quite substantially (by 13%) from 54% in 2011 to 67% in 2014 but decreased again thereafter. The most recent (2016) figure is the same as the average, and very similar to the 61% of respondents in the *Nature* survey who reported that they were not (in 2020) undertaking a PDF in their native country. I further find that the compound annual growth rate (CAGR) for the South African nationals from 2011 to 2016, at 10%, is lower than the CAGR for the foreign PDFs over that period (15%).

Postdoctoral fellows as highly qualified researchers in the higher education sector

I presented above the increase in the absolute number of PDFs over time but given the increase in the number of doctoral graduates every year, a relational measure is called for. It is provided in the R&D surveys, in the form of researchers in the HE sector with a doctoral degree or equivalent. In 2008 (the earliest year for which these figures are available), PDFs constituted only one in 10 of such researchers. Six years later, this proportion more than doubled (to 21%), but has decreased slightly since then, to 18% in 2019.

PFDs do not only contribute to the human-resource base in numbers, but they spend, on average from 2007 to 2019, 92% of their time performing research (expressed by FTEs as a percentage of HCs), which is much more than the 55% for doctoral students and almost four times the 24% reported for researchers (irrespective of highest qualification) in the HE sector. As Figure 2 below shows, these percentages fluctuate quite noticeably for PDFs prior to 2012 (dipping as far down to 83% in 2011), but they have remained quite stable since then and have not deviated more than 2 to 4% from the averages for all three subgroups.

Figure 2: Full-time equivalent as percentage of headcount for PhD students, postdoctoral fellows and researchers in the higher education sector, 2007–2019.

Discussion and Conclusion

The OECD (2021) recently noted a lack of good evidence base on which to design sound policy and practices in the management of PDFs. In this paper I illustrate how (what can be presumed as) relatively standard R&D-survey data may be put to good use to provide an informative picture of PDFs in a country, especially if it is analysed within the local context. Combining such pictures could allow for insightful multi-country comparisons of PDFs that are less likely to be marred by biases of surveys conducted by journals and scientific magazines that depend on their readerships as their main sources of data.

The most recent South African R&D survey shows a significant growth of PDFs who are employed in the South African HE sector, from approximately 300 in 2001 to more than 2 800 in 2019. The growth seems to have decelerated in the past few years and since 2010 is comparable with that observed for at least two other countries. Even at the current pace, the increase in PDFs is not necessarily indicative of a healthy national system of innovation. Growth in PDFs tends to be associated with economic recessions (Powell, 2012) that translate into limited growth in R&D funds, making it increasingly hard for PDFs to find permanent employment (Ahmed et al., 2015). In South Africa, the increase in PDFs has been accompanied by a declining number of permanent junior staff (Cloete, Bunting & van Schalkwyk, 2022), and my calculations show that PDFs have doubled their representation among HE staff with doctoral degrees. Together, these findings suggest that PDFs are part of a growing trend to “casualise” the South African academic workforce (Kerr 2020) by South African universities, under economic strain, that are attempting to sustain their research by appointing increasing numbers of PDFs, but without much prospect of those PDFs gaining permanent employment.

On a more positive note, my results show that the South African HE sector has the ability to attract PDFs from other countries at a scale that is comparable to the global average, and the growth in those “international” PDFs has been 1,5 times higher than that recorded for the South African nationals. Nevertheless, the NRF’s new funding framework prescribes that universities’ applications for its postdoctoral funding must be aligned with the foundation’s “equity target” of “80% of South African citizens and permanent residents” (NRF 2021). Before the implementation of the framework, only 59% of the 799 PDFs that the NRF funded were South African citizens or permanent residents (DST, 2019a). It is therefore not surprising that the new framework has been described as a short-sighted development that does not seem to appreciate the importance of attracting foreign talent to the country (Mouton et al. 2021) and is likely to stifle the contribution of international PDFs to South Africa’s science system and the country’s development (van Schalkwyk, van Lill & Cloete, 2021).

The representation of PDFs among PhD-qualified researchers in the HE sector doubled from 2008 to 2016, whereafter it declined slightly. It is important to bear in mind that from 2011 to 2019, the percentage of staff members in the HE sector who hold a doctoral degree has increased quite dramatically, from 36% to 48% [Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET), 2021]. This increase has been driven by new strategic plans and policies implemented in the past few years to achieve a target of 75% of HE-sector staff with a PhD, as set by the South African government’s macroeconomic growth plan in 2011 [National Planning Commission (NPC), 2011]. If this had not been the case, it is likely that the percentage of PDFs among PhD-qualified researchers in the HE sector would not have decreased.

The main rationale for PDFs’ appointments is that they conduct research and thereby contribute to knowledge production. My analysis of R&D survey results shows that South African PDFs in the HE sector spend on average much more of their time performing research than researchers – and even PhD students – in the same sector do. However, South African policy statements (DST, 2016 & 2019b) and qualitative research (Simmonds & Bitzer 2018) indicate that PDFs in the country are also increasingly required to assist permanently employed academics with other duties, in particular supervision of PhD students, as well as teaching in undergraduate programmes.

The figures sourced from the R&D surveys remain incomplete in many respects, and ideally a complete survey (even audit) of the current PDFs in the South African system should be undertaken. If not anonymous, the data collected will also allow one to conduct bibliometric analyses on the productivity, research collaborations, networks, and citation visibility of South African PDFs. The need for such analyses has been identified by the author’s recent scoping review (Prozesky, 2021) as a major gap in the literature on PDFs, not only in South Africa, but globally.

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